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Concept of *Maya* through the Lens of Aurobindo's Integral Vedanta

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Abstract:

Sri Aurobindo propounded the Integral Vedanta, a philosophy discarding the dualistic approach of traditional Vedanta and conforming with the Advaita Vedanta of Sankara. However, Aurobindo contradicts with Sankara, in the latter's Illusionist Advaita addressing the world as an illusion or *maya* against the Reality of the existence of Spirit. The present paper seeks to unravel Aurobindo's nuanced approach of Harmony between the empirical world and the spiritual realm of the Absolute, Brahman. The research, further, is an attempt to delve into Sri Aurobindo's treatment of *maya* in his selected works.

Keywords: Traditional Vedanta, Integral Vedanta, Illusionist Vedanta, *Maya*, Brahman, Harmony/ Oneness.

The spiritual seekers are, from the time immemorial, striving to attain Existence, Truth-Consciousness, and Delight or *Sacchidanana*, the Absolute. Indian ancient scriptures- Veda, Upanishads, and the *Bhagavad Gita* paint a comprehensive picture of the Brahman as *Sacchidananda*, claiming It to be the immanent and the immutable one. The Vedas propound a dualistic approach towards the Creator and the creation claiming both as two different entities. Advaita Vedanta, a philosophy developed by Sankara, following a non-dualistic approach, strongly claims that both Brahman and the world are One:

The Samkhya philosophy of India separates pure existence from energy and lands upon the dualism of spirit and nature (*purusa* and *prakrti*). The Vedanta of Shamkara also separates the two and preserves its nondualism by declaring cosmic energy as the energy of ignorance or nescience (*avidya, maya*), and therefore unreal from the standpoint of pure self-luminous existence (*purusa, Brahman*). (Chaudhuri 7)

Samkhya “is the process of rejecting the phenomenal world by regarding it as *maya* or illusion to arrive at the Absolute” (Patoa 136).

The Vedas categorise *maya* as the *adaivi maya* and the *daivi maya*. “That which belongs to the Gods is called *Daivi maya* and that which belongs to the *Asuras* is called *Adaivi maya* (Vinitha 2). The researcher posits that the *adaivi maya* is “the root cause of the universe- something inherent in our mind” (3). This *maya* belongs to the lower mental and is “a part of negative magical deceptive power that should be conquered” (3). The Rig Veda describes the *daivi maya* as “the energy or power which belongs to God’s own nature” (4). This form of *maya* pertains to the higher mental. Upanishads equate *maya* and *prakriti* and assert that the world is created by *Purusha* out of *maya* or *prakriti*. This *prakriti* or *maya* is supposed to be inheriting the three *gunas*- *rajas*, *tamas*, and *sattwa*- in it. It is said that the Absolute is devoid of these *gunas*, though they exist as powers of the former to help him in concealing his supreme spiritual nature.

Sri Aurobindo, the great Indian mystic, writer, and philosopher follows the philosophy of Sankara’s Advaita Vedanta, though with certain reservations. In *The Life Divine*, Sri Aurobindo asserts that existence of human beings on the earth is responsible for all their ‘doing, becoming and creating’ (120). He, further, explains beautifully that just as an artist- a poet, painter, or a musician- does not invent anything during the creation of any piece of art, but he only “develop(s) some potentiality in his unmanifested self into a form of manifestation...” the same is the case

with this phenomenal world and the Eternal One. “All creation or becoming is nothing but this self-manifestation” (120). The Divine, thus, manifests in Its creation, “it is one existence, one force, one delight of being which concentrates itself at various points” (121). It implies that the whole creation is a part, a fragment of the divine:

Therefore whatever comes into the world, seeks nothing but this, to be, to arrive at the intended form, to enlarge its self-existence in that form, to develop, manifest, increase, realise infinitely the consciousness and the power that is in it, to have the delight of coming into manifestation, the delight of the form of being, the delight of the rhythm of consciousness, the delight of the play of force and to aggrandise and perfect that delight by whatever means is possible, in whatever direction, through whatever idea of itself may be suggested to it by Existence, the Conscious-Force, the Delight active within its deepest being. (Aurobindo, *Life Divine* 121)

Matter intends to evolve in its physical form as well as in its levels of consciousness and this evolution is the true Bliss aspired for by the whole creation. Existence, Conscious-Force, and Delight are present in every being and persuade its container to evolve further.

A materialistic being considers this material world the reality, on the other hand, an ascetic or a spiritual being considers the Spirit or Brahman the reality. However, Sri Aurobindo advocates a synthesis of the two and declares both being Real. He says, “Materialism like spiritual Monism arrives at a Maya that is and yet is not, - is, for it is present and compelling, is not, for it is phenomenal and transitory in its works” (Aurobindo, *The Life Divine* 23). While discussing Aurobindo’s views on Integralism, Haridas Chaudhari explains:

It would be improper to characterize integralism as either monism or pluralism, because reality in its inmost essence is conceived here as beyond the scope of the concepts of unity and plurality. But that does not mean that monism and pluralism are to be regarded as meaningless philosophical jargon. Since thought is, in the view of integralism, an instrument of self-articulation

of reality, monism and pluralism are, in ultimate analysis, two complementary half-truths insofar as they seek to express the two inseparable aspects of the world of manifestation. (135)

Thus, reality is neither absolute unity nor an absolute plurality, but a harmony between the two. S. Radhakrishnan defines Reality as, “an organism, furnished with a multiplicity of organs and manifestations of life” (440). He further adds:

The true is the whole, and the untrue is the fragmentary or the limited. The finite is real in so far as it is an organic unity, organic with the whole life of the Absolute. We all exist in and not apart from God. The Absolute is a single, all-inclusive system. The finite, we say, is an expression of the spiritual principle, although the Vedanta does not regard it as an exhaustive expression of the spirit. (Radhakrishnan 440)

Thus, both the finite, empirical world as well as the infinite Absolute are true and Real. “The one-sided dependence and the logical inconceivability of the relation between the Ultimate Reality and the world are brought out by the word ‘maya’.” (Radhakrishnan 35)

Sri Aurobindo posits that Advaita conforms with the Oneness of Brahman and does not indulge in any illusion of Truth and Falsehood, Brahman and non-Brahman and so forth:

The real Monism, the true Advaita, is that which admits all things as the one Brahman and does not seek to bisect Its existence into two incompatible entities, an eternal Truth and an eternal Falsehood, Brahman and non-Brahman, Self and non-Self, a real Self and an unreal, yet perpetual *maya*. (*The Life Divine* 35)

Thus, even what is attributed as *maya* in the process of creation, is also real and not an illusion. *Maya* is the power that creates dualism in the world, Advaita of Sri Aurobindo strongly approves both the powers to be One.

Aurobindo asserts that evolution is preceded by an involution, a process of self-absorption of conscious-being into Matter. Once the consciousness enters into Matter, the latter intends to evolve into “formal being, living being, thinking being” and as a final step, the being realises the existence-consciousness-bliss already within it in a latent form. It has become evident now that all is Sacchidananda. But the operation of this Reality still needs to be explored:

Sri Aurobindo refused the main concept of Indian philosophy that states that the World is a Maya(illusion) and to live as a renunciate was the only way. He says that it is possible to transcend human nature and to transform it and to live on the earth as a free and advanced individual with a dynamic consciousness and a divine nature that can perceive the truth of things and proceed on the basis of inner oneness, inward unity, love and light. (Rao 263)

He aspires for a divine consciousness that dilutes ignorance or *avidya/maya* and enables human beings to perceive Existence, Truth-Consciousness, and Delight in the phenomenal world itself.

An infinite consciousness is continuously working towards the attainment of Sat, Chit, Ananda- the ultimate Truth:

Infinite consciousness in its infinite action can produce only infinite results; to settle upon a fixed Truth or order of truths and build a world in conformity with that which is fixed, demands a selective faculty of knowledge commissioned to shape finite appearance out of the infinite Reality. (Aurobindo, *The Life Divine* 123)

The finite world emerges out of Brahman, the infinite Reality.

The power applied to create this finite world out of infinity is given the name “*Maya*” by the Vedic seers:

Maya meant for them [Vedic seers] the power of infinite consciousness to comprehend, contain in itself and measure out, that is to say, to form- for form is delimitation- Name and Shape out of the vast illimitable Truth of infinite existence. (*The Life Divine* 123)

According to traditional Vedanta, *Maya* is illusion of Mind, that bars the consciousness from perceiving Truth and Reality. Sri Aurobindo calls it the “Lower *Maya*”.

The power that synthesises every form and shape of the phenomenal world with the Divine, is termed the “Higher *Maya*” by him:

Thus, *Maya* is not an ignorance, a separation from the totality of the truth, but a transcendental power that is the expression of a divine integral knowledge, where each and every force and form that manifest is united in a totality of truth. If I see a beautiful painting, it is not an illusion that separates me from the Infinite, God, the Divine, but is a unique expression of the Godhead rendered in a unique form by the power of *Maya*. (Posner 79)

The lower mental *Maya*, conforming to Sankara and the traditional Vedantic view, creates illusion of separateness between the phenomenal world and the Eternal. In the Higher supramental *Maya*, “each” and “all” are united into Oneness, both “coexist in the inseparable unity of the one truth and the multiple symbol” (Aurobindo, *The Life Divine* 124)

Aurobindo posits that the illusionist Advaitins could not distinguish between the lower and the higher *Maya* and confused this lower or mental *Maya* to be the creator of this world. Had it been true, the world would have been “an inexplicable paradox and a fixed yet floating nightmare of conscious existence” (Aurobindo, *The Life Divine* 124). He expresses his doubt over Samkara’s *mayavada* as world illusion and says, “... maya cannot play its role without a subject, who receives the illusion” (Vinitha 96). He conveys that Brahman, the Pure Existent and the pure consciousness, real itself, cannot create illusion or an illusive world. This way, *maya*, the creative power of the

Divine, can never be an illusion. “Brahman perceives the world with its pure consciousness, the world must be real and must be nothing but Brahman, because Brahman alone is real” (97).

The Advaitins conclude that the world and its forces, shapes, forms are just the forms of Brahman and not the Brahman itself. These forms are, in fact, the creation of *maya*. Morey adds:

Maya is the supreme and universal consciousness and force of the Eternal and Infinite and, being by its very nature unbound and illimitable, it can put forth many states of consciousness at a time, many dispositions of its Force, without ceasing to be the same consciousness-force for ever. (Morey 75-76)

Such an existence will keep hanging between being illusive or real. The concept of Mind as the creator of the world does not hold any ground. It is just an instrument of Sacchidananda in the process of involution and evolution. However, the world is not conceived in the universal Mind, on the contrary, it is the birth or manifestation of the beyond-Mind into forms of itself:

In the Mind, the multiplicity takes precedence and the conscious sense of the universal oneness is lost, whereas in the Supermind there is the consciousness of the Oneness, i.e., the One in the Many, and the Many in the One. Supermind works as an integrating principle, and considers the apparent opposites as matter and mind, nature and spirit, world and God, the many and the One as “two inseparable poles of the same indivisible and all-comprehensive reality.” “Truth-Consciousness” emphasizes Supermind's awareness of itself as holding multiplicity in unity and “Real-Idea” is understood as “effective self-awareness.” Supermind is thus seen as a creative subjectivity or Brahman's self-knowledge creating the reality of the universe. (Kumar 78)

Sri Aurobindo believes that Mind, the lower mental is the abode of *maya*, *avidya* that leads a materialist to reject the existence of Spirit, and an ascetic to discard the reality of Matter. Once Mind is evolved into Supermind, the “consciousness of Oneness” is generated.

In “Brahman, Purusha, Ishwara — Maya, Prakriti, Shakti” (Book 2 Chapter II), *The Life Divine*, Sri Aurobindo makes an attempt to explain Absolute or Reality as indeterminable, indefinable, and inconceivable by “finite and defining Mind” (337):

To begin this journey of discovery, Sri Aurobindo indicates that to know the source of the determination in the cosmos, to know the Real Ideas and cosmic determinates that are trying to manifest in creation, we must examine Satchitananda Itself; in particular, its first triune, Sat – the pure Existent, the Being. (Posner 211)

Atman, the cosmic Self; *Purusha*, the Conscious Being; and *Iswara*, the Divine Being; are believed to be the three fundamental aspects in seeking the *Sat* element.

Sri Aurobindo expresses that the *Atman* or the cosmic Self uses the power of *maya* to conceive the idea of creating the universe. Roy Posner observes that Sri Aurobindo draws the role of *Atman*/ Cosmic Self as:

... Atman (Self) through the power of Maya has the capacity to create/imagine possibilities; to supports and inform, but not to dynamically execute, making things happen. It can imagine the universe in its various aspects, but not execute that; make it real in the universe. (It is therefore conceptually creative, but not dynamically executive.) (Posner 216).

In *Essays on the Gita*, Sri Aurobindo explains that the *Bhagavad Gita* claims a superiority of the spiritual power over the phenomenal developments of “the senses or of life or of light, its spiritual power intelligence, energy, strength, manhood, ascetic force that are proper to the Supreme Prakriti” (273). He further elaborates that that force, light, and power of spirit is the “eternal seed” which “is the power of spiritual being, the conscious will in the being.” The spiritual being emanates this seed into Brahman that causes the phenomenal existence with its help. This seed is, thus, the root of all the essential qualities- senses, force, light, life, and power-and “constitutes their swabhava” (274) The seeker must understand that these essential qualities of the Divine are different from their

worldly expressions which reflect the lower nature of this phenomenal existence. The three *gunas* – *rajas*, *tamas*, and *sattwa*- are not the “pure actions” of the divine’s supreme spiritual nature. On the other hand, they are just the lower derivations of spiritual nature. Interestingly enough, Sri Aurobindo explains that in order to get near to the Godhead, one not only need to give up sins, but also transcend virtue and *sattwic* actions. However, it does not imply that even virtue and *sattwic* actions are devoid of the Divine. The Divine is present in the “becomings, forms, and affections of the lower nature,” and in the “sattwic” too, but “they are only phenomena in his being created out of it by the action of ego and the ignorance”:

The ignorance presents everything to us in an inverted vision and at least a partially falsified experience. We imagine that the soul is in the body, almost a result and derivation from the body; even we so feel it: but it is the body that is in the soul and a result and derivation from the soul...

This ignorance or *avidya* is a result of the lower nature of the three *gunas*. This is a *maya*, a power of illusion.

It does not mean that the supreme spiritual nature or all the senses, force, light, and power are false or an illusion, or that all this is non-existent:

... but that it bewilders our knowledge, creates false values, envelops us in ego, mentality, sense, physicality, limited intelligence and there conceals from us the supreme truth of our existence. This illusive *Maya* hides from us the Divine that we are, the infinite and imperishable spirit. (Aurobinod 276)

As proclaimed by Aurobindo in his explanation of the teachings in the Gita, This *Maya* is Divine and is claimed by the Godhead as “this is my divine *Maya* of the *gunas*” (qtd. in *Essays on Gita* 276). This *maya* is Divine, but is a derivation of the lower nature of the Divine. “It is a cosmic veil which the Godhead has spun around our understanding” (Aurobindo, *Essays on Gita* 277).

In *The Life Divine*, he delineates the concept of Brahman as One who is indivisible, and immutable. This is the Supreme Power that controls the will of everything existing in the phenomenal world:

It is only our relative consciousness, alarmed or baffled by the phenomenon of evil, ignorance and pain in the cosmos, that seeks to deliver the Brahman from responsibility for Itself and its workings by erecting some opposite principle, Maya or Mara, conscious Devil or self-existent principle of evil. There is one Lord and Self and the many are only His representations and becomings. (36)

Explaining further, he says:

If then the world is a dream or an illusion or a mistake, it is a dream originated and willed by the Self in its totality and not only originated and willed, but supported and perpetually entertained. Moreover, it is a dream existing in a Reality and the stuff of which it is made is that Reality, for Brahman must be the material of the world as well as its base and continent. (36)

In support of his argument on the Reality and Unity of Brahman and Its creation, he puts forward a beautiful example of a gold vessel and utters that “if the gold of which the vessel is made is real, how shall we suppose that the vessel itself is a mirage?” (36). Hence, Brahman is the Reality, how could His creation be unreal.

Works Cited:

1. Aurobindo, Sri. *Essays on the Gita*. Sri Aurobindo Ashram Trust.
2. ---. *The Life Divine*, Sri Aurobindo Ashram Trust. 2006.
3. Chaudhuri, Haridas. The Integralism of Sri Aurobindo. *Philosophy East and West*, Vol.3, Jul., 1953, pp. 131-136. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/1397259>

4. ---. The Philosophy and Yoga of Sri Aurobindo. *Philosophy East and West*, Jan., 1972, Vol. 22, No. 1 (Jan., 1972), pp. 5-14. University of Hawaii Press. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/1397955>
5. Kumar, K Pratap. Sri Aurobindo's Theory of Spiritual Evolution. *International Multidisciplinary Conference on "Knowledge Sharing, Technological Advancements and Sustainable Development"(IMC2k18)*, pp. 71-79. 2018.
6. Morey, Matthew W. Sri Aurobindo's Lila: The Nature of Divine Play According to Integral Advaita. *Integral Review*. July 2012, Vol. 8, No. 1, pp. 68-84.
7. Patoa, Nishikant. "Yoga for the Change of Consciousness: An Integral Vision of Sri Aurobindo". *International Research Journal of Interdisciplinary & Multidisciplinary Studies (IRJIMS)*. Volume-I, Issue-I, February 2015, pp. 135-140.
8. Posner, Roy. *An Analysis of Sri Aurobindo's The Life Divine*. pdf. 2022.
9. Radhakrishnan, S. "The Vedanta Philosophy".
<https://www.journals.uchicago.edu/doi/pdf/10.1086/intejethi.24.4.2376777>
10. Rao, Peesapati Venkateswara. "Sri Aurobindo's Integral Yoga Its Implications" *Journal of Emerging Technologies and Innovative Research (JETIR)*, February 2019, Volume 6, Issue 2. Pp.259-68. www.jetir.org
11. Vineeta. The Maya Hermeneutics in the philosophy of Swami Vivekanand and Sri Aurobindo: A Comparative Study. <http://hdl.handle.net/10603/411942>. 2010.